

NOTES

Complex Formation of Tl (I) and In (III) with 5-Nitro-Salicylic Acid

P. V. Khadikar* and W. V. Bhagwat

In continuation of our previous work¹⁻³, on "5-nitro-salicylic acid as complex forming ligand" we have now studied the complex formation of 5-nitro-salicylic acid with Tl(I) and In(III).

Potentiometric titrations of 1 : 1 mixture of Tl(I) and 5-nitro-salicylic acid (5NSA) and In(III) and 5NSA with alkali show a sharp inflection at two equivalents of alkali. This clearly shows that chelation has taken place due to which the protonic hydrogen of the hydroxyl group of 5NSA has been released along with the replacement of the hydrogen from the carboxylic group. The chelation reaction may be represented as :

Potentiometric titrations of 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 mixture of In(III) and 5NSA with alkali show inflections at 4 and 6 equivalents of alkali which correspond to the formation of 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 complexes between In(III) and 5NSA. The reaction taking place may be represented by the following equations :

Potentiometric titrations of 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 mixture of Tl(I) and 5NSA show inflection at two equivalents of alkali, indicating the formation of only mono-Tl(I)-5-nitro-salicylate according to the equation (1).

Conductometric titrations of Tl(I) and 5NSA, and In(III) and 5NSA, in the ratios 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 also confirm the results obtained by potentiometric studies.

The formation of 1 : 1 complex between Tl(I) and 5NSA has been further confirmed by conductometric study employing Nayar and Pande's method⁴ and Job's method of continuous variations⁵ at concentrations $M/40$, $M/60$ and $M/80$.

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Chemical Laboratories,
Madhav Science College,
Ujjain, (M.P.)

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* To whom the correspondence should be made, Permanent address :—18, Vyayam Shala Gali, Ujjain (M.P.).

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